
CHIANTI

An Astrophysical Database for Emission Line Spectroscopy

CHIANTI TECHNICAL REPORT No. 35

The CHIANTI total recombination rate files (trparams)

1 Overview

Generally, radiative and dielectronic recombination rates are calculated and published separately and their rates are stored in the CHIANTI `rrparams` and `drparams` files, respectively. Further details of these files are given in Technical Reports 7 and 14.

Nahar & Pradhan (1992) described a method to calculate the radiative and dielectronic rates together, yielding a single total recombination rate. The authors subsequently calculated data for many ions and some of these data were added to CHIANTI 6 (Dere et al., 2009). The data are stored in `trparams` files.

This document describes the `trparams` file format, explains how they are read, and lists the ions for which the data are available.

2 File format

The `trparams` file has a simple format, given in Table 1, where rate coefficients are given as published. Fits to the data are not performed.

Table 1: Data format for the `trparams` files.

Line	Format	Parameter
1	i5	Number of temperatures
2	2e12.4	First temperature (K) and rate coefficient ($\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)
3	2e12.4	Second temperature (K) and rate coefficient ($\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)
4	2e12.4	etc.

The data ends with a line containing only ‘-1’, followed by free format strings giving comments and references.

3 Reading the `trparams` files

The `trparams` file is read with the IDL routine `ch_tot_recomb`. For example:

```
IDL> log_temp=findgen(11)/10+4.  
IDL> rate=ch_tot_recomb('fe_2',10.^log_temp)
```

The tabulated rates are interpolated to yield the rates at the requested temperatures.

The routine `recomb_rate` returns the total recombination rate for any ion, which normally means that the separate radiative and dielectronic recombination rates are read and summed. If the `trparams` file exists, then `recomb_rate` calls `ch_tot_recomb` to get the total rate. *If all three files exist for an ion, i.e., radiative, dielectronic and total, then `recomb_rate` prioritizes the total recombination file.*

The advanced ion models introduced in CHIANTI 11 (Dufresne et al., 2024) do not use the `trparams` data, but instead use the separate radiative and dielectronic recombination data. Also, the dielectronic recombination suppression formula (Technical Report 17) can *not* applied to the total recombination rates.

4 Ions

As of May 2026, there are `trparams` files for six ions in CHIANTI: Fe II, Fe III, Fe IV, Fe V, Fe VI, Ni III.

References

- Dere, K. P., Landi, E., Young, P. R., et al. 2009, *A&A*, 498, 915, doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/200911712
- Dufresne, R. P., Del Zanna, G., Young, P. R., et al. 2024, *ApJ*, 974, 71, doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/ad6765
- Nahar, S. N., & Pradhan, A. K. 1992, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 68, 1488, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.68.1488